

ACADEMIC HARDINESS AND SCHOOL BELONGINGNESS AS PREDICTORS OF ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG PSYCHOLOGY STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 1

Pages: 25-40

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2439

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13883352

Manuscript Accepted: 08-26-2024

Academic Hardiness and School Belongingness as Predictors of Academic Stress among Psychology Students

Carl Danielle W. Buenaventura,* Erica L. Alcalá, Ricaella Marie C. Bordeos, Camille R. Canlobo, Georgette Pearl B. Cruzat, Hanna Jane B. De Grano, Daniela D. Del Rosario, Jammie R. Ocampo, Anna Rochelle G. Tamayo, Symon M. Carpiso

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study performed a multiple regression analysis to determine whether academic hardiness and school belongingness could be seen as predictors of academic stress. Psychology students at the Polytechnic University of the Philippines Sto. Tomas, Batangas who were in the Psychology course were involved in the research (N=131) and were sampled using a combination of snowball and convenience sampling. The sampled participants were sent a Google form using social media, such as Facebook, that contained the three research instruments that measured the 3 variables. These instruments were the “Revised Academic Hardiness Scale”, “Perception of Academic Stress Scale”, and “School Belongingness Scale”. The data was collected and then put under multiple regression analysis using the “Jamovi” software. Results show that academic hardiness does not predict participants' perceived academic stress. This hypothesis holds that there is no association between students' academic hardiness and academic stress. In contrast, school belongingness revealed that there is a weak negative correlation with academic stress, and it is proposed that it predicts academic stress among students.

Keywords: *psychology, likert-scales, academic hardiness, school belongingness, academic stress*

Introduction

Stress has become part of students' academic life due to the various internal and external expectations placed upon their shoulders. Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to the problems associated with academic stress as transitions occur at an individual and social level. It therefore, becomes imperative to understand the sources and impact of academic stress in order to derive adequate and efficient intervention strategies (Reddy et al., 2018). There is growing awareness that students' experiences of stress may impede academic success, compromise mental health, and promote substance use. Nearly half (49%) of all students reported feeling a great deal of stress on a daily basis and 31% reported feeling somewhat stressed. Females reported significantly higher levels of stress than males (Leonard et al., 2015).

Delving into stress in its generality opens the discussion for one of the researchers' variables in mind, Academic Stress. Academic stress is a commonly reported affective state by high school students that can be accompanied by unwanted and unhelpful short- and long-term implications including a low sense of school belonging (Abdollahi et al., 2020). Studies have shown that most students experience high levels of academic stress (Choi, Lee, Yoo, & Ko, 2019; Rajoo, Karam, & Abdul Aziz, 2019). Studies have shown that school belonging can develop positive emotional well-being, motivation for academic success, and can secure students from the risks of academic stress (Abdollahi & Noltemeyer, 2018; Allen, Vella- Brodrick, & Waters, 2017; Tong, Reynolds, Lee, & Liu, 2019). A sense of belonging to school is defined as a student's perception about feeling accepted, valued, and cared for within their school environment (Goodenow & Grady, 1993, as cited in, Abdollahi et al., 2020).

Research shows that high school students in the U.S. are struggling to feel a sense of belonging at school, with just 49% saying they feel like they are part of their school community. The pandemic has taken a toll on student well-being as well as their sense of belonging, and 41% of high school students say the events of the past two years made them feel less connected to peers and teachers (Evans, 2022). The need to belong resonates widely as a fundamental motivation to maintain close, continual human bonds. This commentary integrates findings and conclusions from the special issue of the Australian Journal of Psychology focused on belongingness and loneliness. Deficient belongingness, including specifically belonging in schools, is linked to high loneliness, low well-being, poor adjustment, low co-vitality (socioemotional health), impaired sleep, and other problems (Baumeister & Robson, 2021). To label the motivation for social connection as a “need,” Baumeister and Leary (1995) documented that low belongingness was linked to assorted problems with both mental and physical health. Arslan (2021) found that social exclusion and low belongingness were correlated with multiple mental health problems and low overall well-being in a sample of high school students in Turkey.

The characteristics of the academic hardiness development of each individual are different. The most influencing factor is the environment. Environmental differences also affect student achievement, such as one news source in online media which states that high school students in Aceh have started competing at the national level. Academic hardiness is a personality characteristic that can differentiate students who avoid challenging academic tasks and other students who dare to pursue this type of challenge (Fajriani et al., 2021).

Academic hardiness may mediate the relationship between academic stress and school belonging. It is comprised of three components:

commitment, challenge, and control. Commitment involves the motivation and drive to achieve academically, despite competing demands that may exist (e.g., negative peer pressure, responsibilities within the family). Challenge involves perceiving academic difficulties as a normal and common aspect of the educational experience that may lead to further opportunities for personal growth and success. Control involves self-awareness over one's own ability to achieve positive academic outcomes and use emotional self-regulation and coping skills to manage academic stress (Benishek, Feldman, Shipon, Mecham, & Lopez, 2005, as cited in Abdollahi et al., 2020). Based on the findings of this study, a sense of belonging to school and academic hardiness are able to predict academic stress in students. The findings of this study suggest that academic hardiness mediates the relationship between school belonging and academic stress in Iranian high schools (Abdollahi et al., 2020).

This study will aim to assess the strength of the relationship between academic stress and the predictor variables, namely, academic hardiness and school belongingness. However, it is important to note that the research only focuses on the particular population of psychology students of Polytechnic University of the Philippines Sto. Tomas Campus. Acknowledging this gap, allows future researchers to conduct similar studies in other places. With the future findings in mind, the researchers promote a more open and vulnerable school atmosphere by suggesting semestral mental health week which may consist of mental health practitioners lending a helping hand in providing information about dealing with school environment, dealing with academic stress, enhancing academic hardiness, boosting school belongingness, and student counseling to make schools a more appealing place to belong in.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the perceived level of academic hardiness among the participants?
2. What is the level of perceived school belongingness of the participants?
3. What is the level of academic stress perceived by the participants?
4. Is there a significant relationship among the participants' academic stress, academic hardiness, and school belongingness?
5. Do academic hardiness and sense of belongingness predict the likelihood of academic stress for students?

Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative research design was utilized by the researchers to collect and analyze data, more specifically they used a predictive correlational design. The main focus of predictive research is forecasting, or predicting, results, repercussions, expenses, or effects. In order to forecast something that has never been attempted, tested, or proposed before, this kind of research attempts to extrapolate from the examination of current events, laws, or other entities (Wollman, 2018). The goal of the predictive correlational design is to ascertain how one of the examined constructs relates to the other and whether the independent or predictor variable can be used to predict the dependent variable or criterion (Pulido, 2022). The predictive research was used to ascertain how Psychology students' academic stress were affected by academic hardiness and school belongingness.

The investigators have to have a predictor variable and a criterion variable in order to use this design. Therefore, in research that try to predict a certain phenomenon or outcome, this design is important (IvyPanda, 2023). The predictive correlational research design is appropriate for this type of study because the researchers' goal is to figure out the predictive power of the two quantitative independent variables (academic hardiness, and school belongingness) on a quantitative dependent variable's (academic stress) state or existence. Additionally for the purpose of researching issues in education and other social contexts, correlational designs such as predictive correlational research designs are quite helpful (Gall, Gall, & Borg, 2007).

Respondents

The target respondents to be used for the study were Psychology college students from the Polytechnic University of the Philippines Sto. Tomas, Batangas. They were chosen by the researchers because they wanted to evaluate if academic stress could be predicted by academic hardiness and school belongingness specifically, meaning students were to be the primary respondents for the research. Additionally, college-age students and young adults experience the highest rates of chronic and harmful stress, according to certain studies (Kerr, 2023). The sampling size according to Green (1991) states that a study that uses a multivariable regression or correlation analysis such as a predictive correlational study must be calculated using the formula $N > 50 + 8m$ where N is the minimum sample size and m is the number of predictor/independent variables (VanVoorhis, 2007). Using the formula the minimum number of respondents is 66 students. However, the researchers decided to select 131 participants because most statisticians concur that in order to get meaningful findings, a sample size of 100 is required (Akman, 2023). The researchers sampled 131 Psychology college students which is above the minimum number of responders needed for the study. The researchers used non-probability sampling, specifically convenience sampling and snowball sampling to obtain the sample. As a nonprobability sampling technique, convenience sampling chooses units for the sample based on those that are most convenient for the researcher to reach. This might be the result of factors like close proximity geographically, availability at a specific moment, or interest in taking part in the study. Snowball sampling involves enlisting new units into the sample through the recruitment of existing units. (Nikolopoulou, 2023) A It is stated by Freedman (1999) that although there has been progress in the application of many statistical techniques suggesting challenges in concluding causality

from statistical associations, the use of inferential statistics in a non-probabilistic sample is permissible. Hubbard et al. (2019), who points out that because statistical conclusions have limitations, researchers should also take the context and practical significance of the results into consideration while doing research, further supported this. The researchers have taken caution of the limitations of using a parametric test with a non-probability sample, particularly in terms of generalizability.

Instrument

Questionnaires were used to efficiently gather information from the participants. Specifically, standardized questionnaires were used, so researchers can ensure that the data collected is reliable and can be compared across different studies. All the questions were aligned with the study's objective and focused on addressing the research problem. Various scales were applied to collect data on distinct variables.

Specifically, the researchers used the following instruments:

Revised Academic Hardiness Scale - The Revised Academic Hardiness Scale (RAHS) is a psychological tool designed to measure academic hardiness, which refers to a student's resilience in coping with academic stress and challenges. Initially developed by Lois A. Benishek and Lopez in 2001 as the Academic Hardiness Scale (AHS), the scale was revised in 2005 due to issues with internal reliability in one of its components (Creed et al., 2013). The RAHS assesses three dimensions of academic hardiness: Commitment, Control, and Challenge, using a 40-item self-report questionnaire with a 4-point Likert scale (Weigold et al., 2015). Studies across various student samples, including those in late elementary school, college, and undergraduate levels, have validated the scale's psychometric properties, showing satisfactory Cronbach's alpha coefficients for its subscales (Commitment, $\alpha = .80$; Control, $\alpha = .82$; Challenge, $\alpha = .81$) (Kamtsios and Karagiannopoulou, 2011; Weigold et al., 2015; Creed et al., 2013; Kamtsios and Karagiannopoulou, 2015; Karagiannopoulou and Kamtsios, 2016). Recent research by Ayuningtias et al. (2023) confirmed a high Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.963 for RAHS among Senior High School students, indicating excellent internal consistency and reliability in measuring the intended construct of academic hardiness.

Perception of Academic Stress Scale - The Perception of Academic Stress Scale (PASS), developed by Dalia Bedewy and Adel Gabriel in 2015, measures students' perceived stress related to academic activities. The scale includes 18 self-report items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, from "Strongly agree" (1) to "Strongly disagree" (5). It assesses stress dimensions related to academic expectations, faculty workload and examinations, and students' academic self-perception. Example statements include "Competition with my peers for grades is quite intense" and "The examination questions are usually difficult." The original PASS demonstrated reliability and validity among 100 students aged 19 to 26 at the University of Tanta in Egypt, although the original language of the scale is unspecified (Dias & Franca, 2021). It has been used internationally, including in studies from the United States (James, 2017), Australia (Fisher & Pidgeon, 2018), and India (Sharma, 2018). Dias and Franca (2021) used the English version, confirming its reliability with a McDonald's omega (ω) of 0.86 and Cronbach's alpha (α) of 0.83, with a 95% confidence interval between 0.79 and 0.85. These metrics indicate that PASS is a reliable and valid tool for assessing academic stress perceptions.

School Belongingness Scale - The School Belongingness Scale (SBS) was developed by Gokmen Arslan and Erdinc Duru in 2016 as a psychometric tool to measure students' sense of belonging in the school environment. The SBS assesses students' feelings of acceptance and inclusion within their school community, focusing on aspects such as peer and teacher-student relationships, and overall satisfaction with the school. The scale comprises two subscales: the Social Exclusion Scale (SES) and the Social Inclusion Scale (SIS), with items rated on a four-point scale from almost never (1) to almost always (4). Higher scores indicate a stronger sense of belonging. Arslan and Duru tested the SBS on 562 students from an urban area in Turkey and concluded that the scale is effective in measuring school belongingness, demonstrating relationships with students' connection to school, enjoyment of learning, confidence, and happiness. A subsequent analysis by Arslan in 2019, involving 223 elementary students, confirmed the SBS model as a good fit for data, with latent construct reliability coefficients ranging from .72 to .79. Internal reliability coefficients were .70 for SES, .73 for SIS, and .76 for the overall SBS, indicating consistency and reliability in measuring the intended constructs. These findings support the SBS as a reliable tool for assessing school belongingness among elementary students.

Procedure

The researchers allotted time and effort in searching appropriate standardized questionnaires suitable for the target participants and for effectively measuring the variables in this study.

All the collected standardized questionnaires were compiled into an online survey format using Google Forms. The survey was divided into four main sections, with the final section further divided into subparts, each containing questions related to different variables in the study. The researchers sought out qualified participants who met the predefined eligibility criteria by using online platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. Before gaining access to the survey questions, participants were required to review the data privacy act and agree to the terms and conditions, ensuring that the researchers respected the privacy of the respondents. Moreover, to confirm the eligibility of the participants, the online survey included inquiries about the demographic profiles (age and gender) of the participants and confirmation of their enrollment in the Bachelor of Science in Psychology program, specifically in the third year. Names were not required, with the option for participants to provide their names. The survey included an attached informed consent form and other necessary materials. The predefined questionnaires were at the end of the survey, containing queries related to academic hardiness,

school belongingness, and academic stress.

In order to ensure the reliability of the study, the researchers thoroughly examined and curated the responses, leading to the exclusion of those that did not meet the established requirements. Despite this, the researchers successfully reached their desired sample size of 50 third-year students enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Psychology program at Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Sto. Tomas Campus. Subsequently, the researchers employed software to analyze and interpret the collected response data.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatments were used by the researchers to analyze and evaluate the data from the questionnaires that were answered by the respondents.

Mean. The total sum of the values in a sample divided by the total number of values in your sample yields the mean, also called the average (Hurley, 2023). These means were used to show in a concise and interpretable manner the scores of the responders.

Standard Deviation. The standard deviation, which can be computed as the square root of the variance, is a statistic that expresses how dispersed a dataset is in relation to its mean. By calculating the deviation of each data point from the mean, the standard deviation may be computed as the square root of variance. The standard deviation increases with the degree of data dispersion because a bigger deviation exists within the data collection when the data points deviate from the mean (Hargrave, 2023).

Pearson Product Moment Correlation- The strength of a linear relationship between two variables is measured by the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, or Pearson correlation coefficient for short, and is represented by the symbol r . In essence, a Pearson product-moment correlation looks for the best fit line between the data of two variables, and the Pearson correlation coefficient, or r , shows how far apart each data point is from the best fit line (Hahs-Vaughn, 2023). This study used Pearson correlation to look at the correlations between the variables of academic stress, school belongingness, and academic toughness. By performing this statistical treatment, the researchers were able to assess whether these variables had a relationship to begin with, and how they seemingly affected one another.

Multiple Regression. Multiple regression, which is often called multiple linear regression, is a statistical method that involves using multiple independent variables to predict the value of a dependent variable (Hayes, 2023). Additionally, its purpose is to create a model that describes how the independent variables are related to the dependent variable in a linear manner. Basically, multiple regression is used when researchers want to analyze the relationship between a dependent variable and two or more independent variables. In this study, multiple regression was used to measure on how academic stress relates to academic hardiness, and school belongingness. This statistical technique helped the researchers to determine and measure how academic hardiness and school belongingness influenced academic stress simultaneously.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers strictly followed the American Psychological Association's (APA) ethical principles to maintain and ensure an ethically based study. Gaining trust of the participants is important. To show truthfulness and formality, the researchers obtained an informed consent which involves a clear explanation of the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of this study, enabling them to make a decision about whether to participate or not, without any pressure or coercion. The study used an online survey form lowering the risk of any potential physical harm the study might cause. Also, the researchers avoided sensitive and triggering questions that might cause participants psychological and emotional harm, and if there is, the participants were free to withdraw their participation in the study. The researchers prioritized the welfare of the participants involved.

Other than that, researchers ensured the privacy of the respondents were respected and were not subjected to any discrimination, harassment, or unfair treatment. Protection and confidentiality of private information and participant responses were prioritized, ensuring anonymity for all participants. To maintain anonymity, participants were not required to provide their government name and were only requested for an optional name. Deception was strictly avoided throughout the research process, and if used at all, it was minimized by providing participants with detailed information during the informed consent process and thorough explanations during the debriefing. The study was conducted with the utmost integrity and without any fraudulent intentions.

All information obtained during the study was handled with utmost ethical care and securely protected, with only the researchers having access to the Google Form. The researchers were informed to exercise reasonable judgments and restricted from forming any form of biases. The rights of the participants to withdraw at any point of the study were acknowledged and respected. The researchers took full responsibility for the ethical conduct of the study and diligently adhered to these ethical guidelines throughout the entire research process.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the statistical results, as well as a thorough discussion of the studies and findings' interpretations.

Table 1 presents the level of Academic Hardiness of the respondents in terms of the three subscales, namely, commitment, control, and challenge, as well as their overall academic hardiness.

Table 1. *Level of Academic Hardiness of the Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Overall Academic Hardiness	2.85	Moderate	0.22
Commitment	3.09	Moderate	0.35
Control	2.71	Moderate	0.45
Challenge	2.64	Moderate	0.31

Table 1 illustrates the findings from the domains of commitment, control, and challenge, which aid in assessing the Academic Hardiness of Bachelor of Science Psychology students. The participants' average Commitment score is 3.09 (SD = 0.35), which is deemed moderate. This demonstrates that Bachelor of Science Psychology students devote a reasonable amount of time, effort, and concentration to their studies and exhibit a moderate degree of interest and participation in their academic activities.

The mean control score was 2.71 (SD=0.45), which is moderate. This demonstrates that they can manage stress, overcome obstacles, and deal with academic expectations. They may not always excel at problem-solving, but they generally strike a balance between dealing with stress and suffering academic disappointments while looking for methods to enhance their performance.

The mean challenge score was 2.64 (SD=0.31), which is moderate. Students at this level engage moderately in academic challenges, encountering projects and coursework that take them slightly outside of their comfort zone. Students in this zone typically strike a healthy mix between challenging their abilities and managing their workload effectively.

Finally, the mean score for overall academic hardiness was 2.85 (SD=0.22). This showed moderate academic hardiness. Students at this level display a balanced approach to dealing with academic problems. They may have some resilience and determination, but they do not constantly have an extremely strong or unwavering attitude toward overcoming academic challenges.

Bakar et al. (2021) conducted a study to describe the profile of students' academic hardiness in general as well as the profile of academic resilience aspects at MAS Imam Syafii, Aceh Besar, and found that the general profile of academic hardiness in their population was moderate. Another study conducted by Aprodita (2021), which attempted to investigate the association between students' quality of college life and academic hardiness, found a similar interpretation of their results, with the majority of their participants having a moderate level of academic hardiness.

Table 2. *Level of School Belongingness of the Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Overall School Belongingness	3.11	Moderate	0.47
Social Acceptance	2.98	Moderate	0.58
Social Exclusion	3.2	Moderate	0.54

The level of School Belongingness of the students in the Polytechnic University of the Philippines is presented in table 13 accompanied by the subscales of social acceptance, and exclusion. The social acceptance mean of the participants scored 2.98 (SD=0.58) which amounts to a moderate value. This pertains to the fact that the students generally experience social acceptance in a moderate and average amount among peers, and schoolmates within school premises.

The social exclusion mean totals to 3.2 (SD=0.54) which exhibits a moderate value. This refers to a leveled and moderate feelings of exclusion within school grounds. At this level, students experience a modest amount of exclusion and indicate an average level of lack of participation in social networks in the campus.

Lastly, the overall mean for School Belongingness amounted to an average of 3.11 (SD=0.47). This indicates moderate experience of School Belongingness. Students perceive an adequate level of general acceptance, support, and inclusion they feel among their mates. They may experience feelings of inclusion and acceptance in a general manner.

In a study that aims to find the relationship of school belonging and socialemotional, behavioral, motivational, and academic outcomes by Korpershoek et al. (2020), it was found that there is little to moderate association with school belonging and various ranges of student outcomes. Additionally, Sulimani-Aidan and Melkman (2022) studied school belonging and hope and found moderate association of school belonging with hope.

Table 3. *Level of Academic Stress of the Respondents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
Overall Perceived Academic Stress	3.18	Moderate	0.46
Academic Expectations	2.96	Moderate	0.78
Faculty Work and Examinations	3.30	Moderate	0.64
Self-Perceptions	3.04	Moderate	0.60

Table 3 displays the Academic Stress level of the participants across three subscales: academic expectations, faculty workload and examinations, and self-perceptions, along with their overall academic stress score.

The table highlights outcomes derived from the areas of academic expectations, faculty responsibilities, and examinations, which were

employed to examine the Academic Stress of the participants. The domain of academic expectations yielded a mean score of 2.96 (SD = 0.78) which means the respondents have a moderate level of academic stress in terms of academic expectations. The indicated score implies that students are facing a reasonable level of pressure or tension due to the expectations set in their academic pursuits. It indicates a middle ground, not too high or too low, in terms of the stress levels associated with the academic demands and standards placed on them.

Mean score for the area of faculty workload and examinations yielded 3.30 (SD = 0.64). This indicates that psychology students have a moderate level of stress related to faculty work and examinations. Also, mean score suggests that students face a notable but manageable amount of pressure due to a demanding workload, frequent exams, or challenging assignments. The stress is not extreme but is still noteworthy, suggesting a balance between challenges and manageability in their academic responsibilities.

On the other hand, the domain of self-perceptions yielded a mean score of 3.04 (SD = 0.60) which similarly implies that students have moderate levels of stress in terms of self-perceptions. It indicates that students encounter a moderate level of pressure or anxiety influenced by their self-perceived academic capabilities, achievements and performance.

Lastly, the overall academic stress of the participants yielded a mean score of 3.18 (SD= 0.46) which means that the overall stress perceived by the respondents is at a moderate level. Moderate level suggests that students experience noticeable but not overwhelming pressure and tension. While facing challenges and demands in their studies, the impact on their overall well-being is likely more manageable compared to those experiencing extreme or high levels of academic stress.

The overall moderate level of stress is similar to the findings of Bataineh (2013) as cited by Ahmad et al. (2021) which found that college students experience moderate levels of stress. These stresses were generated by factors such as academic overloads, recurring semester workloads, challenging exams which can be classified as faculty workload and examinations, inconvenient course structures, insufficient study time, low motivation, and elevated family expectations which can be classified as under self-perceptions and academic expectations.

Moreover, to support this, findings from the study of Ahmad et al. (2021) found that the students' general stress level is moderate, aligning with findings from previous studies (Abouserie, 1994; Bataineh, 2013). Ahmad (2021) emphasized that moderate stress level appears to stem from various administrative issues and academic demands within the college environment. These can include pressure, expectations, workloads, examinations, financial issues, self-perceptions, motivations and so on. Same findings can be found in the study of Albashtawy et al. (2023) which discovered that the majority of university students experience moderate levels of stress which garnered 75.1% of students where stressors are assessed to be environmental and academic.

Karvinen et al. (2018) study findings indicate that most students in the College of Education experience a moderate level of academic stress, with none experiencing a low level. According to them, primary sources of academic stress among these students include teachers, academic performance, exams, peer pressure, time management, and course workload which can be similarly classified as academic expectations, faculty workload, examinations, and self-perceptions.

Table 4. Correlation among the variables

Variables		Academic Hardiness	Academic Stress	School Belongingness
Academic Hardiness	Pearson's r	-		
	p-value			
Academic Stress	Pearson's r	-0.024	-	
	p-value	0.781		
School Belongingness	Pearson's r	0.298	-0.286	-
	p-value	<.001	<.001	

Table 4 displays the correlation between various variables. This emphasizes the outcomes of correlation between academic stress and academic hardiness, and academic and academic belongingness.

Findings indicated that there is no significant correlation between academic stress and academic hardiness, with a correlation coefficient of -0.024 and a p-value of 0.781. The p-value (0.781) is higher than the commonly used significance level of 0.05. A higher p-value implies weaker evidence against the null hypothesis. In this context, a p-value of 0.781 suggests that the observed correlation could likely occur by random chance, and there is a failure to reject the null hypothesis, which typically states no significant relationship between the variables.

In a study conducted by Bartone et al. (2009), correlation between academic hardiness and academic stress yielded a non-significant outcome ($r = -.19, p < .01$). Bartone et al. found people with a high level of hardiness typically view new experiences as thrilling and challenging rather than upsetting and disruptive. They also feel that they have enough control and commitment over their personal resources to lead their lives in the way they desire and a strong sense of devotion to their pursuits. This distinct method of evaluation hardly appears; they are shielded from the negative effects of stress by pressures that they perceive positively and by their conviction that they can effectively manage life's demands. Findings suggested that by hardiness, students are adding effort as the best way to cope up with the stress brought by it (Bartone, 2009).

Furthermore, Hanurawan's study in 2022 also resulted in a non-significant outcome ($p > .05$) in which he used grade 12 students. He suggested that there may be additional variables that the study did not yield a significant relationship between academic hardiness and academic stress in kids in grades 12. Hardiness alone may not have the same effect on academic stress as other elements like workload, time management, or personal situations. Also, he emphasized that there is a chance that the school's unique cultural or environmental elements shaped the connection between academic stress and hardiness.

Nugraha et al. (2023) conducted a study that also showed a non-significant result in finding a correlation between academic hardiness and academic distress ($r = -0.09$, $p > 0.05$). The study discovered that the participants' degree of academic distress was not significantly impacted by their degree of academic hardiness which implies that other variables might be of greater significance in predicting students' academic distress.

On the other hand, results indicated a meaningful association between academic stress and school belongingness ($r = -0.286$, $p < .001$). Results were indicating a weak negative correlation. A negative correlation means that overall academic stress and overall school belongingness have an inverse relationship to one another. The p -value of less than 0.001 suggests that this correlation is statistically significant. In statistical terms, a p -value below a certain threshold (commonly 0.05) indicates that the observed relationship is unlikely to have occurred by chance alone. Therefore, the results suggest that the association between academic stress and school belongingness is not random, and there is a genuine and significant relationship between these two variables in the studied context. Furthermore, in this research's context, as the academic stress decreases the school belongingness increases. This is the same as when academic stress increases, school belongingness decreases.

Recent study by Latifa (2023) stated that a factor to decrease academic stress for college students is to get social support in the form of self-esteem support and belonging support. According to her study, social support includes belonging support. Belonging support is defined as the availability of companionship for activities, significantly influences students' academic stress levels with a negative correlation. In essence, higher levels of belonging support are associated with reduced academic stress, as having someone to engage in activities reduces feelings of isolation and fosters trust in others. This increased sense of belonging tends to improve mood positively.

Additionally, in a study of Hyder and Gul (2020) where they studied the relationship of classroom sense of community, academic achievement, and academic stress. They cited a definition of community by McMillian and Chavis (1986) which says that a community is characterized by the sense of belonging those members experience, where they feel significant to one another and to the collective group. It encompasses a shared conviction that members' needs will be fulfilled through their dedicated commitment to being part of the community. This connection fosters a supportive environment, encouraging mutual care and reinforcing the idea that each member plays a crucial role in the overall well-being of the group. The study resulted with a finding that academic stress and classroom sense of community has a significant relationship.

Skipper (2023) conducted a study of what is the relationship among sense of belonging, mental well-being, and academic stress. Results showed that high sense of belongingness is correlated with lower levels of academic stress and higher levels of mental well-being. This suggests that a strong sense of belongingness can help reduce stress levels especially in an academic context.

Arslan and Coskun (2022) conducted a study to explore the impact of a sense of school belongingness on diverse psychosocial and well-being outcomes in adolescents facing academic challenges. Results showed that a strong association exists between a sense of belonging in school and reduced psychological and emotional distress among adolescents who are academically at risk. Although the direct correlation between school belongingness and academic stress isn't explicitly explored, the observed positive impacts of school belongingness on psychological wellbeing and distress imply its potential role in alleviating academic stress among academically at-risk adolescents. The probable reason behind is school belongingness fosters a positive atmosphere, offers social support, and enhances psychological wellbeing, aiding students in handling academic difficulties and lessening stress. They concluded that a sense of connection and inclusion in the school community can provide students with a supportive foundation, motivation, and resilience, acting as a buffer against the pressures of academic stress.

An analysis using multiple regression was run to check the hypothesized predictive association between academic stress and the two predictor variables of the study. To assure that all assumptions necessary for multiple regression are met, the researchers conducted an assumption checking test. The assumptions and their corresponding statistical tests were the Durbin-Watson test to make sure there was no autocorrelation, Collinearity statistics to know there was little to no multicollinearity, and Shapiro-Wilk to test the normal distribution of the data.

Table 5. Durbin-Watson Test for Autocorrelation

<i>Autocorrelation</i>	<i>DW Statistic</i>	<i>p</i>
-0.126	2.24	0.164

The autocorrelation Durbin-Watson test gave a DW statistic of 2.24, which is close to 2. When evaluating the significance of the DW statistic and its relationship to autocorrelation, a value larger than 2.0 typically suggests a negative correlation. However, the DW statistic is near to 2 implies that the assumption of independent errors is not violated in this scenario. A score approaching 2 indicates no autocorrelation, according to the "Durbin-Watson Significance Tables". Another study states that if a Durbin-Watson statistic is close to 2, the residual series is free of autocorrelation at a significance level of 0.05 (Chen, 2016).

Table 6. Collinearity Statistics

Variables	VIF	Tolerance
Academic Hardiness	1.10	0.911
School Belongingness	1.10	0.911

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance under Collinearity Statistics were generated for the predictor variables Academic Hardiness and Academic Belongingness. All variables have low VIF values, with Academic Hardiness and Belongingness being at 1.10. Similarly, the Tolerance levels for all factors are much higher than the threshold limit of 0.1, with both Academic Hardiness and Belongingness at 0.911. In general, a VIF larger than 4 or a tolerance less than 0.25 suggests the likelihood of multicollinearity and requires further investigation. When VIF exceeds 10 or tolerance is less than 0.1, there is significant multicollinearity to be handled. This indicates that the VIF and the Tolerance computed by the researchers show no multicollinearity and that the results of the multiple regression analysis are valid and reliable (Bhandari, 2023).

Table 7. Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)

Statistic	p
0.982	0.079

To test the normality of the research distribution, Shapiro-Wilk’s was used in assessment. The table indicates the three variables’ overall normality distribution which obtained a p-value of 0.079. This denotes that the distribution of the research is higher than 0.05 and accepts the null hypothesis. Therefore, it implies that the research prominently suggests normal distribution

Table 8. Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
1	.293	.0860	.0717	6.02	0.003

a. Predictors: Academic Hardiness and School Belongingness
 b. Dependent variable: Academic Stress

To test the hypothesis that Academic Stress is predicted by Academic Hardiness and School Belongingness of Psychology college students, the researchers conducted a multiple regression analysis. The test revealed that the combination of the both the Academic Hardiness and School Belongingness values explained 7.17% of the variance in Academic stress, $R^2 = 0.0860$, $F(2, 128) = 6.02$, $p = 0.003$.

The computed correlation value (r) of 0.293 reveals a low positive linear association between Academic Hardiness, School Belongingness and Academic Stress (Cohen et al., 2013). This implies that 2 of these factors have some ability to predict changes in students' Academic Stress. It should be noted however, that it was found there was no correlation between Academic Hardiness and Academic Stress, indicating the inconclusive results of this table. The coefficient of determination R square result of .0860 indicates that the combined model’s contribution of Academic Hardiness and School Belongingness accounts for roughly 8.60% of the variability seen in Academic Stress (Cohen et al., 2013). The Adjusted R Square value of 0.0717, is lower than the R Square value, indicating that including the two predictors in the model enhances the model's explanatory ability. It highlights the importance of these measures while acknowledging that other unconsidered factors influence students' Academic Stress (Cohen et al., 2013).

The significant F-statistic indicates that the predictors and the dependent variable have a meaningful relationship. It must again be taken note however that Academic Hardiness does not contribute to this relationship as this specific predictor variable has no correlation with the outcome variable. The following table will go more in-depth as to which predictor variable contributed more to these statistically significant outcomes (Kutner et al., 2005; Field, 2013; Hair et al., 2014).

Table 9. Model Coefficient-Stress

Predictor	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p	Stand. Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper				Lower	Upper
Intercept	3.724	0.5055	2.723	4.724	7.366	<.001	-	-	-
Belongingness	-0.298	0.0862	0.469	0.128	3.459	<.001	0.3061	0.481	0.131
Hardiness	0.136	0.1804	0.221	0.493	0.753	0.453	0.0667	0.108	0.242

Before performing the multiple regression analysis, a Pearson correlation test was done. According to its results, Academic Hardiness and Academic Stress have no correlation to one another, thus making the regression analysis specifically for Academic Hardiness inconclusive. Despite this, the researchers still used said predictor variable in the regression analysis. The predictor variable which was Academic Hardiness that was assessed by the Likert-scale titled "Revised Academic Hardiness Scale" proved to be not a predictor for Academic Stress, $\beta = 0.0667$, $t(130) = 0.753$, $p = 0.453$ [$B/b = 0.136$, $t(130) = 0.753$, $p = 0.453$]. This means that the level of Academic Hardiness students has no bearing or predictive value for one's Academic Stress.

School Belongingness however, that was scored using the "School Belongingness Scale" was found to be a significant predictor for Academic Stress, $\beta = -0.3061$, $t(130) = -3.459$, $p < .001$ [$B/b = -0.298$, $t(130) = -3.459$, $p < .001$]. This suggests that the level of School Belongingness students feel has significant predictive power with regards to Academic Stress. This means that the higher the School Belongingness the lower the Academic Stress, with negative values showing a negative relationship. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for School Belongingness is -0.298 , meaning that for every unit increase in School Belongingness, one should expect a -0.298 unit drop in Academic Stress. School Belongingness has a standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.3061 , indicating a negative influence that shows as School Belongingness increases by 1-point, Academic stress should drop -0.3061 units. School Belongingness has a T-statistic of -3.459 , which is significant with a $p < 0.001$, supporting the hypothesis that School Belongingness has significant effects on Academic Stress. Furthermore, overall, the 95% confidence interval for the School Belongingness coefficient spans from -0.481 to -0.131 , which is above zero, indicating that School Belongingness has a negative effect on Academic Stress. (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007; Field, 2013; Fox, 2015; Hair et al., 2014).

The findings of this statistical study, specifically about how Academic Hardiness does not predict Academic Stress are supported by other research investigations that provide comparable outcomes. "The Relationship Between Hardiness and Academic Stress in XII Grade Students of X Senior High School," a study conducted in 2022 with the goal of examining the relationship between hardiness and academic stress during the completion of the final project in XIIth grade in students of X Senior High School, found no significant relationship or predictive power between Academic Hardiness and Academic Stress. They explained that numerous variables contribute to pupils' academic stress. Hardiness is insufficient to protect them from the academic stress that can arise at any time. They stressed that people can utilize many coping mechanisms, and these tactics are significantly more important when it comes to stress management than whether they are hardy or not (Putri et al., 2022). Yuningish et al. (2021) found comparable results. Their study sought to evaluate the extent to which social support influences academic distress in 144 Master of Professional Psychology students, using academic hardiness as a mediator. They discovered no link between academic hardiness and academic distress ($r = -0.09$, $p > 0.05$).

The conclusion of "School Belongingness does predict Academic Stress" is supported by numerous studies. Abdollahi et al. (2020) conducted a study to investigate the association between academic stress and sense of school belonging, as well as the mediating influence of academic hardiness. Four hundred and five high school students from six schools in Tehran (Iran) participated in the study. The findings shed light on the underlying process by which poor school belonging can contribute to academic stress in high school pupils. Creating a culture of school belonging, as well as teaching and encouraging academic resilience skills, should be top priorities for all schools looking to reduce academic stress among their students. Sumiati et al. (2023) found that high levels of social support can protect a person from stress-related disease. The findings revealed that social support was inversely connected with academic stress. Furthermore, Skipper Y. (2023) proposed that a sense of belonging predicted increased mental well-being and decreased stress.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researcher concludes the following:

There was a balanced yielded scores in commitment, control, and challenge, thus, resulted in the data of the overall perceived academic hardiness of the participants which indicates that the student participants dealt well in regards with their academic problems. This concluded that the respondents show a sense of commitment when facing demanding academic performance and taking control over challenging academic tasks. On the other hand, the data obtained in the overall perceived school belongingness shows that the participants experienced an average level when exposed to a school environment. This inferred that the participants experienced emotional connection in educational settings as there is moderate data collected in participant's sense of social inclusion and social exclusion.

In addition, the overall academic stress of the participants remained in the moderate range, with slightly higher concerns about self-perception, their sense of school community also reached a similar "moderate" level. This suggests a potential interplay between these factors. While external pressures and self-doubt may cause some stress, a supportive and welcoming school environment could act as a buffer, preventing it from becoming overwhelming. This is further highlighted by the lack of a significant relationship between academic hardiness (a combination of factors like control, challenge, and dedication) and stress levels. This suggests that other factors, such as social support systems or individual coping strategies, might play a more significant role in how students manage and cope with academic pressure.

According to the data obtained using multiple regression, there was no significant relationship between Academic Hardiness and Academic Stress. While in the evaluated data of School Belongingness, it showed a significant relationship with Academic Stress.

Therefore, this concludes that Academic Hardiness does not predict the perceived Academic Stress of the participants. This postulates that the students' academic hardiness has no correlation with academic stress, as the data have shown no relationship between them. On the contrary, School Belongingness demonstrated a weakly negative correlation with Academic Stress and posited that it does predict Academic Stress among the students.

References

- Abdollahi, Abbas & Panahipour, Sana & Tafti, Mahnaz & Allen, Kelly-Ann. (2020). Academic and stress in students of law and psychology in an English University.
- Ahmad, R. (2021, May 5). "A study to assess the level of stress among college students in a selected Govt. College of Nursing, Srinagar, J&K, India". Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2105883.pdf&ved=2ahUKewieluyupGEAxUy1TQHHR5XAmoQFnoECDYQAQ&usg>
- Aihie, O. N., & Ohanaka, B. I. (2019). Perceived Academic Stress among Undergraduate Students in a Nigerian University. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 9(2), 56–66. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jesr-2019-0013>
- Akman, S. (2023b, May 2). Research type and sample size: Is there a correlation?. Research type and sample size: Is there a correlation? <https://forms.app/en/blog/correlation-between-research-typeandsamplesize?fbclid=IwAR0KLUKIKaFqetT>
- Akrim, A., & Umiarso, U. (2022). Conceptualizing of Academic Hardiness During Covid-19 pandemic of an Islamic Senior High School in Malang, East Java. *Journal of Innovation in Educational and Cultural Research*, 3(2), 200-206. <http://www.jiecr.org/index.php/jiecr/article/viewFile/94/44>
- Albashtawy, M. (2023, June 29). Stress Factors, Stress Levels, and Coping Mechanisms among University Students. *Scientific World Journal*. Retrieved from <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/tswj/2023/2026971/>
- Allen, K. A. (2022, January 22). The Science of School Belonging: How schools are key to helping kids feel like they belong. *Psychology Today*. Retrieved November 12, 2023, from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/sense-belonging/202201/thescience-school-belonging>
- Allen, K., Boyle, C., Wong, D. K., Johnson, R. G., & May, F. J. (2022). School belonging as an essential component of positive psychology in schools. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 159–172). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003228158-21>
- Allen, K., Kern, M. L., Vella-Brodrick, D., Hattie, J., & Waters, L. (2016). What Schools Need to Know About Fostering School Belonging: a Metaanalysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(1), 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-016-9389-8>
- Allen, K., Slaten, C. D., Arslan, G., Roffey, S., Craig, H., & Vella-Brodrick, D. (2021). School Belonging: The importance of student and teacher relationships. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 525–550).
- Allen, K.A (2019, August 9). 5 ways to boost students' sense of school belonging. (2023, May 26). *Monash Education*. <https://www.monash.edu/education/teachspace/articles/5-ways-toboost-students-sense-of-school-belonging>
- Allen, KA., Gallo, B., Ryan, T. et al. (2023). Examining predictors of school belonging using a socio-ecological perspective. *J Child Fam Stud* 32, 2804–2819 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-022-02305-1>
- Allen, Kelly-Ann & Slaten, Christopher & Arslan, Gökmen & Roffey, Sue & Craig, Heather & Vella-Brodrick, Dianne. (2021). School Belonging: The Importance of Student and Teacher Relationships. [10.1007/978-3-030-64537-3_21](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64537-3_21)
- Alsulami, S., Omar, Z. A., Binnwejjim, M., Alhamdan, F., Aldrees, A. M., AlBawardi, A. A., Alsohim, M. S., & Alhabeeb, M. (2018). Perception of academic stress among Health Science Preparatory Program students in two Saudi universities. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, Volume 9, 159–164. <https://doi.org/10.2147/amep.s143151>
- Alsulami, S., Omar, Z. A., Binnwejjim, M., Alhamdan, F., Aldrees, A. M., AlBawardi, A. A., Alsohim, M. S., & Alhabeeb, M. (2018). Perception of academic stress among Health Science Preparatory Program students in two Saudi universities. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, Volume 9, 159–164. <https://doi.org/10.2147/amep.s143151>
- Aprodita, N. (2021). The relationship between quality of college life and academic hardiness among college students. Retrieved from <https://download.garuda.kemdikbud.go.id/article.php?article=2925839&val=25814&title>
- Aprodita, N. P. (2021). The relationship between quality of college life and academic hardiness among college students. *Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan & Konseling* Vol, 7(1).
- Arslan, G., & Coşkun, M. (2022). School belongingness in academically at-risk adolescents: Addressing psychosocial functioning and psychological well-being. *Journal of Happiness and Health*, 3(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.47602/johav.v3i1.9>
- Arslan, G., Allen, K., & Ryan, T. (2020). Exploring the Impacts of School Belonging on Youth Wellbeing and Mental Health among Turkish Adolescents. *Child Indicators Research*, 13(5), 1619–1635. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-020-09721-z>

- Arslan, G., Allen, KA. & Ryan, T. Exploring the Impacts of School Belonging on Youth Wellbeing and Mental Health among Turkish Adolescents. *Child Ind Res* 13, 1619–1635 (2020).
- Aspelmeier, J. E., Love, M. M., McGill, L. A., Elliott, A. N., & Pierce, T. W. (2012). Self-esteem, locus of control, college adjustment, and GPA among first- and continuing-generation students: A moderator model of generational status. *Research in Higher Education*, 53, 755–781. doi:10.1007/s11162-011-9252-1
- Aspelmeier, J. E., Love, M. M., McGill, L. A., Elliott, A. N., & Pierce, T. W. (2012). Self-esteem, locus of control, college adjustment, and GPA among first- and continuing-generation students: A moderator model of generational status. *Research in Higher Education*, 53, 755–781. doi:10.1007/s11162-011-9252-1
- Bakar, A., Fajriani, F., & Marsela, F. (2021). The Profile of Students' Academic Hardiness: A Descriptive Study. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272447155_Exploring_relations_between_academic_hardiness_and_academic_stressors_in_university_undergraduates
- Bakar, A., Fajriani, F., Husen, M., & Shafira, N. (2022). Academic hardiness and active procrastination: levels and correlation among university students. *Enlighten (Jurnal Bimbingan Dan Konseling Islam)*, 5(1), 15- 24. <https://doi.org/10.32505/enlighten.v5i1.3871>
- Barbayannis, G., Bandari, M., Zheng, X., Baquerizo, H., Pecor, K. W., & Ming, X. (2022). Academic stress and mental well-being in college students: Correlations, affected groups, and COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.886344>
- Barbayannis, G., Bandari, M., Zheng, X., Baquerizo, H., Pecor, K. W., & Ming, X. (2022). Academic stress and mental well-being in college students: Correlations, affected groups, and COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.886344>
- Bashir, A., Amir, A., & Bajwa, K. M. (2019). An investigation of stressors among university students: A qualitative approach. *UCP Management Review (UCPMR)*, 3(1), 5-24.
- Bhandari, A. (2023). Multicollinearity: Causes, effects and detection using VIF (updated 2023). Retrieved from https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2020/03/what-ismulticollinearity/?fbclid=IwAR3cPX_wVEfl8pCdKaUcYzcIvlu4YZLOB5JyZEVZBrN-o4cwFioON-2ZN8w
- Biggs, Amanda, et al. "Lazarus and Folkman's Psychological Stress and Coping Theory." *The Handbook of Stress and Health*, 18 Feb. 2017, pp. 349–364, onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118993811.ch21, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118993811.ch21>.
- Bowen, J. (2021, October 21). Why is it Important for Students to Feel a Sense of Belonging at School? 'Students Choose to be in Environments That Make Them Feel a Sense of Fit,' Says Associate Professor DeLeon Gray. *College of Education News*. <https://ced.ncsu.edu/news/2021/10/21/why-is-it-important-for-studentsto-feel-a-sense-of-belonging-at-school-students-choose-to-be-in-environments-that-make-them-feel-a-sense-of-fit-says-associateprofessor-deleon-gra/>
- Braun, A. M. (2019). Psychological inclusion: Considering students' feelings of belongingness and the benefits for academic achievement. *The SAGE handbook on inclusive and diversity in education*, 66-75.
- Cardoso-Pulido, M. J., Guijarro-Ojeda, J. R., & Pérez-Valverde, C. (2022, May 18). A correlational predictive study of teacher well-being and professional success in Foreign Language Student Teachers. https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/10/10/1720?fbclid=IwAR2Cb1-b39KTjSGVuVoTbTuOEkybNT_AIHk01dAmRFyXZq_Fzps9JARTIg
- Casuso-Holgado, M. J., Moreno-Morales, N., Labajos-Manzanares, M. T., & Montero-Bancalero, F. J. (2019). The association between perceived health symptoms and academic stress in Spanish Higher Education students. *European Journal of Education and Psychology*, 12(2), 109- 123.
- Casuso-Holgado, M. J., Moreno-Morales, N., Labajos-Manzanares, M. T., & Montero-Bancalero, F. J. (2019). The association between perceived health symptoms and academic stress in Spanish higher education students. *European Journal of Education and Psychology*, 12(2), 109– 123. <https://doi.org/10.30552/ejep.v12i2.277>
- Chawla, K., & Sachdeva, V. (2017). Domains of stress and coping strategies used by 1st year medical students. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. <https://doi.org/10.5455/njppp.2017.7.1040623102017>
- Chen, Y. (2016). Spatial autocorrelation approaches to testing residuals from least squares regression. Retrieved from <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0146865>
- Cheng, Y. et al. (2019). Academic Hardiness and Academic Self-Efficacy in graduate studies. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Academic+Hardiness+and+School+Belongingness+as+predictors+of+Academic+Stress&id=EJ1220639>
- Christopher D. Slaten, Jonathan K. Ferguson, Kelly-Ann Allen, Dianne-Vella Brodrick & Lea Waters (2021). School Belonging: A Review of the History, Current Trends, and Future Directions, *Educational and Developmental Psychologist*, 33:1, 1-15, DOI:

10.1017/edp.2016.6

Classroom Sense of Community and Academic Achievement: Mediating role of Academic Hardiness and Moderating Role of Gender. Diamond Scientific Publishing . Retrieved November 11, 2023, from <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/14-513.pdf>

Cohen, T., Morse, L., Panter, & Turan, N. (2013). (PDF) cohen et al. 2013 JRP supplementary tables S1-S4. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263344664_Cohen_et_al_2013_JRP_Supplementary_Tables_S1-S4

Conway, G. Marquez, V. (2019). School connectedness and academic buoyancy: Insights into filipino college students' experience of academic stress. *Southeast Asia Psychology Journal*, 7, 70-85.

Deng, Y., Cherian, J., Khan, N. U. N., Kumari, K., Sial, M. S., Comite, U., Gavurová, B., & Popp, J. (2022). Family and academic stress and their impact on students' depression level and academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2022.869337>

Deng, Y., Cherian, J., Khan, N. U. N., Kumari, K., Sial, M. S., Comite, U., Gavurová, B., & Popp, J. (2022). Family and academic stress and their impact on students' depression level and academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2022.869337>

Dewi, R., Dalimunthe, R. Z., Matondang, I., Sianipar, E. L., & Dalimunthe, M. B. (2021). Learning Material Development As a Coping Strategy for Managing Student Stress During the Pandemic. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), 28–34. Gul, K. G., & Hyder, I. H. (2020, March 27).

ELN Limited. (2018, January 3). Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs for Learners | Blog | ELN <https://www.eln.co.uk/blog/maslows-hierarchy-of-needs-forlearners#:~:text=In%20the%20third%20level%20of,and%20part%20of%20the%20group>

Espinosa, J. F., Hernández, J., Rodríguez, J. E., Maricarmen, C., & Bermúdez, V. (2020). Influencia del estrés sobre el rendimiento académico. *Archivos venezolanos de farmacología y terapéutica*, 39(1), 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065032>

Evaluation, C. F. E. S. A. (2023, August 31). Sense of belonging. <https://education.nsw.gov.au/student-wellbeing/tell-them-fromme/accessing-and-using-tell-them-from-me-data/tell-them-from-memeasures/-sense-of-belonging>

Fajriani, Fajriani & Bakar, Abu & Marsela, Fitra. (2021). The Profile of Students' Academic Hardiness: A Descriptive Study. 10.2991/assehr.k.210909.105.

Feldhammer-Kahr, M., Arendasy, M., & Paechter, M. (2022). STUDENTS PERCEIVED ACADEMIC STRESS, SENSE OF BELONGING, ADAPTABILITY, SPORTS AND DEPRESSION IN THE SECOND YEAR OF THE PANDEMIC. *Psychological Applications and Trends 2021*. <https://doi.org/10.36315/2022inact018>

Flórez, Y. N., & Sánchez, R. (2020). El Estrés Visto como Reto o Amenaza y la Rumia. Factores de Riesgo a la Salud. *Revista Salud y Administración*, 7(20), 17–27. <https://revista.unsis.edu.mx/index.php/saludyadmon/article/view/182>

Fox. (2015a). *Applied regression analysis and generalized linear models* (3rd ed.). Sage.

Gallardo-Lolandes, Y., Zapata, N. A., Flores, J. A., & Ocaña-Fernández, Y. (2020). Time management and academic stress in lima university students. *International Journal of Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v9n9p32>

Gallardo-Lolandes, Y., Zapata, N. A., Flores, J. A., & Ocaña-Fernández, Y. (2020). Time management and academic stress in lima university students. *International Journal of Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v9n9p32>

Hahs-Vaughn. (2023). Pearson correlation coefficient. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/pearsoncorrelation-coefficient?fbclid=IwAR0p27y8E2t9xbnYVwCqYaFB0t1jPP7dou00eZf4 aA8282zTzMtyazzoK98>

Hair, J., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in Business Research. Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128/full/html>

Handara, M. and Irafahmi, D. (2022). Hardiness, social support, and academic stress of students working on bachelor's thesis during the pandemic. *Journal of Educational Health and Community Psychology*, 11(4), 766. <https://doi.org/10.12928/jehcp.v11i4.24382>

Harahap, N. R. A., Badrujaman, A., & Hidayat, D. R. (2022). Determinants of academic stress in students. *Bisma the Journal of Counseling*, 6(3), 335–345. <https://doi.org/10.23887/bisma.v6i3.53548>

Hardiness as a mediator for the relationship between school belonging and academic. <https://ejle.eu/index.php/EJLE/article/view/62>

Hasel, Kurosh & Abdolhoseini, Amir & Ganji, Puyesh. (2011). Hardiness Training and Perceived Stress among College Students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 30. 1354-1358. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.262.

- Hayes, A. (2023, April 29). Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) Definition, Formula, and Example. Investopedia. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/mlr.asp>
- Huber, E. (2021). An Investigation of Social Belongingness as a Predictor of Physiological and Psychological Responses to Exam Stress. <https://doi.org/10.17615/b9rv-as60>
- IvyPanda. (2023). Correlational research: Explanatory and predictive designs. https://ivypanda.com/essays/correlational-research-explanatory-andpredictivedesigns/?fbclid=IwAR0L_jjAadw0M9oxY3v1YeImj9aJtLRzADRF03mZAUXiR1aASS4CDwikYk8
- Jdaitawi, M. (2015). Social connectedness, academic, non-academic behaviors related to self-regulation among university students in Saudi Arabia. *International Education Studies*, 8(2), 84-100. doi: 10.5539/ies.v8n2p84
- Jianping, G., Roslan, S., Zaremohzzabieh, Z., & Geok, S. K. (2023). Improving hardiness among university students: A meta-analysis of Intervention Studies. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.994453/full>
- Karaman, M. A., Lerma, E., Vela, J. C., & Watson, J. C. (2019). Predictors of academic stress among college students. *Journal of College Counseling*, 22(1), 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocc.12113>
- Karimah, U., Syamsu, Y., Juntika, N., & Nandang, B. (2021). The Hardiness Profile of Islamic Boarding School Student in Indonesian. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(3), 1806-1813.
- Karvinen, I. (2018, November). The Level of Academic and Environmental Stress among College Students: A Case in the College of Education. *Scientific Research*. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=88342>
- Kelly, Alison & Mulrooney, Hilda. (2019). Student perceptions of belonging at university: a qualitative perspective.. *New Directions in the Teaching of Physical Sciences*. 10.29311/ndtps.v0i14.3238.
- Kerr, E., & Claybourn, C. (2023). Stress in college students: What to know - U.S. news & world report. <https://www.usnews.com/education/bestcolleges/articles/stress-in-college-students-what-to-know>
- Kirby, L. a. J., & Thomas, C. L. (2021b). High-impact teaching practices foster a greater sense of belonging in the college classroom. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 46(3), 368–381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877x.2021.1950659>
- Kirby, L. a. J., & Thomas, C. L. (2021b). High-impact teaching practices foster a greater sense of belonging in the college classroom. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 46(3), 368–381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877x.2021.1950659>
- Kuo, T. M., Tsai, C. C., & Wang, J. C. (2021). Linking web-based learning selfefficacy and learning engagement in MOOCs: The role of online academic hardiness. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 51, 100819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2021.100819>.
- Kutner, M., Nachtsheim, Neter, J., & Christopher. (2005). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/200093046_In_Applied_Linear_Statistical_Models
- Lartey, F. (2013). Impact of Career Planning, Employee Autonomy, and Manager Recognition on Employee Engagement. Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2971042>
- Ma, C. (2023). The academic stress and subjective well-being of graduate nursing students: the mediating role of resilience. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 79(7), 2654-2663. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.15619>
- Maajida Aafreen, M., Vishnu Priya, V., & Gayathri, R. (2018). Effect of stress on academic performance of students in different streams. *Drug Invention Today*, 10(9).
- Maghsoodi, A. H., Ruedas-Gracia, N., & Jiang, G. (2023). Measuring college belongingness: Structure and measurement of the Sense of Social Fit Scale. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 70(4), 424–435. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000668>
- Maghsoodi, A. H., Ruedas-Gracia, N., & Jiang, G. (2023). Measuring college belongingness: Structure and measurement of the Sense of Social Fit Scale. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 70(4), 424–435. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000668>
- Mawarni, A. (2017). The exercise group technique on academic hardiness in senior high school students. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/81594174/The_Exercise_Group_Technique_on_Academic_Hardiness_in_Senior_High_School_Students?uc-sbsw=29712771
- Melhe, M. A., Salah, B. M., & Hayajneh, W. S. (2021). Impact of Training on Positive Thinking for Improving Psychological Hardiness and Reducing Academic Stresses among Academically-late Students. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 21(3), 132-146
- Misra, R., & Castillo, L. G. (2004). Academic stress among college students: Comparison of American and international students. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 11, 132–148. doi:10.1037/1072- 5245.11.2.132
- Mulati, Y. and Purwandari, E. (2022). The role of resilience in coping with academic stress (a meta-analysis study). *Kne Social*

Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v7i18.12387>

Nikolopoulou, K. (2023, June 22). What is Snowball Sampling?: Definition & examples. Scribbr. https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/snowballsampling/?fbclid=IwAR1uma1AU0EIPMXv0uIwH0MT1b2_K8zF_4NVpsrFXvsd5qinzMR6UjvpVM

Nikolopoulou, K. (2023a, June 22). What is convenience sampling?: Definition & examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/convenience-sampling/>

Nor, M. (2022, February 23). Effective coping strategies utilised by medical students for mental health disorders during undergraduate medical education-a scoping review. BMC Medical Education. Retrieved from <https://bmcomeduc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-022-03185-1>

Noson, V. & Shastri, S. (2016). Stress and Academic Performance. The International Journal of Indian Psychology, Vol. 3(Issue 3, No. 4, DIP: 18.01.068/20160303)

Olivera, P. C., Gordillo, P. G., Mejía, H. N., La Fuente Taborga, I., Chacon, A., & Unzueta, A. S. (2023). Academic stress as a predictor of mental health in university students. Cogent Education, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2023.2232686>

Putri, P. K., & Hanurawan, F. (2022). The relationship between hardiness and academic stress in XII grade students of X Senior High School. Retrieved from <https://knepublishing.com/index.php/KnESocial/article/view/12394>

Ralph, M. (2022, December 6). How to cultivate a sense of belonging in schools. Edutopia.

Ramón-Arbués, E., Gea-Caballero, V., Granada-López, J. M., Juárez-Vela, R., Pellicer-García, B., & Antón-Solanas, I. (2020). The prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress and their associated factors in college students. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 17(19), 7001. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17197001>

Ramón-Arbués, E., Gea-Caballero, V., Granada-López, J. M., Juárez-Vela, R., Pellicer-García, B., & Antón-Solanas, I. (2020). The prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress and their associated factors in college students. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 17(19), 7001. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17197001>

Reddy, K. J., Menon, K. R., & Thattil, A. (2018). Academic Stress and its Sources Among University Students. Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal, 11(1), 531–537. <https://doi.org/10.13005/bpj/1404>

Reddy, K. J., Menon, K. R., & Thattil, A. (2018). Academic Stress and its Sources Among University Students. Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal, 11(1), 531–537. <https://doi.org/10.13005/bpj/1404>

Robotham, D. & Julian, C. (2006). Stress and the higher education student: A critical review of the literature. Journal of Further and Higher Education, 30(2), 107-117. doi: 10.1080/03098770600617513

Robotham, D. & Julian, C. (2006). Stress and the higher education student: A critical review of the literature. Journal of Further and Higher Education, 30(2), 107-117. doi: 10.1080/03098770600617513

Skipper, Y. (2023, June 1). The relationship between the sense of belonging, mental wellbeing

Slaten, C. D., Allen, K., Ferguson, J. K., Vella-Brodrick, D., & Waters, L. (2018). A historical account of school belonging. In BRILL eBooks (pp. 7–23). https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004386969_002

Slaten, Christopher & Ferguson, Jonathan & Allen, Kelly-Ann & Vella-Brodrick, Dianne & Waters, Lea. (2016). School Belonging: A Review of the History, Current Trends, and Future Directions. The Educational and Developmental Psychologist. 33. 1-15. 10.1017/edp.2016.6.

Stein, S. J., & Bartone, P. T. (2020). Hardiness: Making stress work for you to achieve your life goals. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley et Sons, Inc. stress. Psychology in the Schools. 57. 10.1002/pits.22339.

Stojanović, M., & Popović Ćitić, B. (2022). Osećaj pripadnosti školi - značaj za pozitivan razvoj i prevenciju problema u ponašanju učenika. Nastava i vaspitanje, 71(3), 403-423. <https://doi.org/10.5937/nasvas2203403S>

Strayhorn, Terrell. (2019). College Students' Sense of Belonging. 10.4324/9781315297293.

Sukup, L. and Clayton, R. (2021). Examining the effects of resilience on stress and academic performance in Business undergraduate college students. <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=School+Belongingness%2c+Academic+Stress+college&id=EJ1379824>

Sumiati, N. T., Sakiinah, M., & Latifa, R. (2023). College students' academic stress during the COVID-19 pandemic: The influence of hardiness, coping strategy, social support, and demographic factors and. Retrieved from <http://journal2.uad.ac.id/index.php/cp/article/view/7271>

Tabachnick, & Fidell. (2007). Validation of the Arabic Version of the Inventory of Coping Strategies of Competitive Sport (ISCCS).

Retrieved from <https://www.scirp.org/reference/ReferencesPapers?ReferenceID=18872> 85

Tan, D., Ho, K., & T'ng, S. (2021). Increasing graduation rate: academic hardiness, academic locus of control, tolerance of ambiguity, students' engagement and automatic negative thoughts. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(17). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v11-i17/11395>

Tholen, R., Wouters, E., Ponnet, K., de Bruyn, S., & Van Hal, G. (2022). Academic Stress, Anxiety, and Depression Among Flemish First-Year Students: The Mediating Role of Sense of Belonging. *Journal of College Student Development* 63(2), 200-217. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2022.0015>.

Tom, S. (2022). Effect of perceived academic stress on college students. *Ymer*, 21(06), 343-352. <https://doi.org/10.37896/ymer21.06/33>

Tosevski, D.L.; Milovancevic, M.P.; Gajic, S.D. Personality and psychopathology of university students. *Curr. Opin. Psychiatry* 2010, 23, 48-52.

Tri, Yuniningsih., Sumedi, P, Nugraha. (2023). Academic Hardiness sebagai Mediator untuk

Trigueros R, Padilla A, Aguilar-Parra JM, Lirola MJ, García-Luengo AV, Rocamora-Pérez P, López-Liria R. The Influence of Teachers on Motivation and Academic Stress and Their Effect on the Learning Strategies of University Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020; 17(23):9089. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17239089>

Trigueros, R., Padilla, A., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Lirola, M., Luengo, A. V. G., Rocamora-Pérez, P., & Liria, R. L. (2020). The influence of teachers on motivation and academic stress and their effect on the learning strategies of university students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(23), 9089. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17239089>

Tus, Jhoselle. (2020). Academic Stress, Academic Motivation, and Its Relationship on the Academic Performance of the Senior High School Students. 8. 29-37. 10.6084/m9.figshare.13174952.v1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345149814_Academic_Stress_Academic_Motivation_and_Its_Relationship_on_the_Academic_Performance_of_the_Senior_High_School_Students

Tus, Jhoselle. (2020). Academic Stress, Academic Motivation, and Its Relationship on the Academic Performance of the Senior High School Students. 8. 29-37. 10.6084/m9.figshare.13174952.v1.

VanVoorhis, C., & Morgan, B. (2007). Understanding power and rules of thumb for determining sample sizes - TQMP. *Understanding Power and Rules of Thumb for Determining Sample Sizes*. <https://www.tqmp.org/RegularArticles/vol03-2/p043/p043.pdf>

Vaziri, C., Ghanbaripannah, A., & Tajalli, P. (2021). Modeling the Cognitive Flexibility and Academic Engagement based on Self-Regulation, Psychological Hardiness and Self-Differentiation with Mediation of Family Functioning in High School Students. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 9(3), 13281-13295. <https://doi.org/10.22038/IJP.2020.50410.4011>.

Wang, J., Chen, Y., Chen, H., Hua, L., Wang, J., Jin, Y., He, L., Chen, Y., & Yao, Y. (2023). The mediating role of coping strategies between depression and social support and the moderating effect of the parent-child relationship in college students returning to school: During the period of the regular prevention and control of COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.991033>

Wardani, Ria. (2020). ACADEMIC HARDINESS, SKILLS, AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING ON NEW STUDENT. *Jurnal Psikologi*. 19. 188-200. 10.14710/jp.19.2.188-200.

Watson, J. C., & Watson, A. A. (2016). Coping self-efficacy and academic stress among Hispanic first-year college students: The moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Journal of College Counseling*, 19, 218-230. doi:10.1002/jocc.12045

Whedon, S. (2023, September 26). Why Students Need to Feel a Sense of Belonging and How To Create It. <http4s://www.panoramaed.com/blog/student-sense-of-belonging>

Wollman, L. (2018). Research Paradigms. *Research paradigms*. https://www.chds.us/coursefiles/research/lectures/research_paradigms/player.html

Yang, C., Chen, A., & Chen, Y. (2021). College students' stress and health in the COVID-19 pandemic: The role of academic workload, separation from school, and fears of contagion. *PLOS ONE*, 16(2), e0246676. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246676>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Carl Danielle W. Buenaventura

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Erica L. Alcalá

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Ricaella Marie C. Bordeos

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Camille R. Canlobo

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Georgette Pearl B. Cruzat

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Hanna Jane B. De Grano

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Daniela D. Del Rosario

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Jammie R. Ocampo

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Anna Rochelle G. Tamayo

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Symon M. Carpiso

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines